

A New Route to Pilosinine and *dl*-6-Ethylpilosinine

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A new method for aminomethylhomo-*r*-lactones as the starting materials for the preparation of pilosinine and *dl*-6-ethylpilosinine has been described. This has been achieved by hydrolysing the corresponding ethyl 1-substituted-3-phthalimidoacetoacetates.

Pilocarpine (IV: R=Et), the chief alkaloid of *Jaborandi*, has been found to consist of *r*-lactone and an imidazole joined through a methylene bridge. For the synthesis of pilocarpine and isopilocarpine, Preobrashenski *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1930, **63**, 460; 1933, **66**, 1536) obtained diazomethyl homopilopyl ketone (I: R=Et) from the chloride of pilopic acid. The former was transformed into the chloro derivative, which with potassium phthalimide gave phthalimidomethyl homopilopyl ketone (II: R=Et). On hydrolysis, the latter gave aminomethyl homopilopyl ketone (III: R=Et) which with KCNS yielded 2-thiol-pilocarpidine. This on oxidation with FeCl₃ and subsequent methylation gave pilocarpine (IV: R=Et). Following a similar procedure, Preobrashenski and Kuleshova (*J. Gen. Chem., U.S.S.R.*, 1945, **15**, 237) have prepared a series of pilocarpine analogues.

Dryamova *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1948, **18**, 1733) condensed 3-hydroxyisocrotic acid lactone with ethyl *r*-ethoxyacetoacetate in presence of sodium ethoxide and obtained ethyl α -ethoxyacetylhomopilosinate (V: R=H). The latter was first hydrolysed by HCl (1:3) and then by HBr to furnish bromomethyl homopilosinyl ketone which with potassium phthalimide gave phthalimidomethyl homopilosinyl ketone [II: R=Et].

In an independent method Dey (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1057), using methylzinc iodide, converted homopilopyl chloride into β -acetonyl- α -ethyl-*r*-butyrolactone (VI). The ozonide (VII) of the benzylidene derivative of the latter on decomposition gave a glyoxal (VIII),

which on treatment with ammonia and formaldehyde and subsequent methylation gave pilocarpine and isopilocarpine (IV: R=Et).

(where R=Et).

In the present investigation for the preparation of pilosinine (IV: R=H), a modified method for the preparation of aminomethyl homopilosinyl ketone (XII: R=H) has been followed. Ethyl 3-phthalimidoacetoacetate (IX: R=H) (Mehrotra and Verma, this *Journal*, 1961, 38, 785) was condensed with 1-ethoxy-3-cyano-2-propene (X) in presence of NaOEt when a deep red product was produced, from which ethyl 1-phthalimidoaceto-2-ethoxymethyl-3-cyanobutyrate (XI: R=H) could not be crystallised. On hydrolysis of this product aminomethyl pilosinyl ketone [XII: R=H] was obtained. The latter was converted into pilosinine in the usual way.

In an attempt to obtain pure product (XI: R=H), an alternative procedure was followed. The propene (X) was condensed with diethyl malonate to afford ethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl-2-ethoxymethyl-3-cyanobutyrate (XIII: R=H). The ethoxymagnesium salt of this compound was condensed with phthalimidoacetyl chloride. The product on steam distillation furnished (XI: R=H) in good yield.

In another preparation, ethyl group was introduced in the methylene bridge of pilosinine. For this purpose, ethyl 1-ethyl-3-phthalimidoacetoacetate (IX: R=Et) (Dixit *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1961, 38, 853) was condensed with (X) in presence of NaOEt to afford (XI: R=Et). After hydrolysis of the latter and treatment with KCNS, it gave *dl*-2-thiol-6-ethylpilosinidine (XIV: R=Et). This was oxidised and methylated to yield *dl*-6-ethylpilosinine (XV: R=Et).

EXPERIMENTAL

Aminomethyl Homopilosinyl Ketone.—In a three-necked flask were placed ethyl 3-phthalimidoacetate (6.87 g., 0.025*M*) and dry ethanol (50 c.c.) and the whole was warmed to dissolve the ester. To this a solution of sodium ethoxide (from 0.58 g. of Na) in 15 c.c. of ethanol was added dropwise with stirring. The deep red mixture was stirred for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour more; 1-ethoxy-3-cyano-2-propene (2.78 g., 0.025*M*) in dry ethanol (15 c.c.) was added during 30 minutes. After allowing the mixture to stand overnight, it was refluxed for 1 hour and cooled. Glacial acetic acid (1.52 g.) was added and the mixture stirred for 15 minutes. The solvent was removed at 40–50° and to the deep red syrupy residue water (20 c.c.) was added. This was extracted with 80, 10, and 10 c.c. portions of benzene. The combined organic layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed to yield 8.78 g. of a deep red residue. This was refluxed with 50% HCl (45 c.c.) for 10 hours in an oil bath at 140°. The mixture was cooled and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated under diminished pressure. The residue was dissolved in water and treated with decolorising charcoal. Water was again removed and the residue kept over solid NaOH in vacuum for 24 hours and then extracted with dry ether-ethanol (1:3; 10 c.c. $\times$ 3). From the organic liquid, the solvent was removed and the residue refluxed with 48% HBr (20 c.c.) for 10 hours in an oil bath at 145°. HBr was completely removed under diminished pressure. The residue was dissolved in dry ethanol (4 c.c.) and freeze-dried when extremely hygroscopic crystals of *aminomethyl homopilosinyl ketone hydrobromide*, m.p. 138° (decomp.), was obtained in 3 g. yield. It was quickly filtered and dried in vacuum over P₂O₅. (Found: C, 35.39; H, 4.84; N, 5.88. Calc. for C₇H₁₂O₃NBr: C, 35.30; H, 5.04; N, 6.00%).

Ethyl 1-Ethoxycarbonyl-2-ethoxymethyl-3-cyanobutyrate.—In a 500 c.c. three-necked flask were placed dry ethanol (100 c.c.) and clean sodium (9.2 g.) and diethyl malonate (80 g.) was added to it, followed by dropwise addition of 1-ethoxy-3-cyano-2-propene (45.5 g.) during 45 minutes. The mixture was refluxed with continued stirring for 1 $\frac{1}{2}$ hours and then cooled. Glacial acetic acid (25 g., 0.42*M*) was then added and the ethanol was removed. To the residue water was added (200 c.c.) and the lower layer of crude ester separated and dried over fused CaCl₂. This was fractionated, collecting 105 g. of the ethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl-ester passing at 192–99°/20 mm, d_{4}^{20} 1.0637; n_D^{20} 1.439. (Found: C, 58.1; H, 8.5. C₁₃H₂₁O₃N requires C, 57.56; H, 7.75%).

Ethyl 1-Phthalimidoaceto-2-ethoxymethyl-3-cyanobutyrate.—Clean magnesium turnings (4.8 g.), dry ethanol (7 c.c.), and dry CCl₄ (1 c.c.) were taken in a three-necked flask and to it were added ethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl-2-ethoxymethyl-3-cyanobutyrate (54.2 g.) and dry ethanol (20 c.c.) at such a rate that a vigorous reaction was maintained. When the reaction had subsided, dry ether (75 c.c.) was added and the mixture refluxed till all the magnesium had dissolved. The solvent was removed and the residue again dissolved in benzene (75 c.c.). The solvent was again removed and the residue was suspended in dry ether (75 c.c.) and phthalimidoacetyl chloride (44.8 g.) in dry ether (500 c.c.) was added with stirring at such a rate that a vigorous reaction was maintained. Finally the reaction mixture was gently refluxed for 2 hours, cooled in an ice bath, washed with water, and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed and the residue was steam-distilled till a clear distillate was obtained. The residue was extracted with 100, 50 and 50 c.c. portions of benzene. The mixed organic layer was filtered and dried over fused CaCl₂. The solvent was completely removed and the residue triturated with dry ethanol (10 c.c.) and left overnight in an ice bath.

Crystals of the desired product (42 g.) were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol when it melted at 106-107°. (Found: C, 61.9; H, 4.8; N, 7.3. $C_{20}H_{22}O_6N$ requires C, 61.9; H, 5.2; N, 7.25%).

This ester (4 g.) when hydrolysed, as described above, gave 1.4 g. of *aminomethyl homopilosinyl ketone hydrobromide*, m.p. 138°. (Found: C, 35.39; H, 4.84; N, 6.08. Calc. for $C_7H_{12}O_3NBr$: C, 35.3; H, 5.04; N, 5.88%). This ketone on treatment with KCNS (2g.) in aqueous solution (0.83g.) gave 0.7 g. of *2-thiol-pilosinidine*, m.p. 202° (lit. m.p. 202.5°). The thiol (0.4 g.) was oxidised by heating with an aqueous solution $FeCl_3$ (2.8 g.) to yield 0.39 g. of white crystalline *pilosinidine nitrate*, m.p. 116° (lit. m.p. 117-18°). This salt (0.3g.) on methylation gave *pilosinine nitrate*, m.p. 168° (lit. m.p. 165-67°), yield 0.19 g.

dl-2-Thiol-6-ethylpilosinidine.—By following a procedure similar to that described above, ethyl 1-ethyl-3-phthalimidoacetate (15.15 g.) was condensed with 1-ethoxy-3-cyano-2-propene (5.55 g.) using metallic sodium (1.15g.) and finally glacial acetic acid (3.3g., >0.05M). The condensed product was hydrolysed first by HCl (75 c.c.) and after the removal of phthalic acid and NH_4Cl , this was further hydrolysed by 48% HBr (40 c.c.). Aminoketone thus obtained was treated with an aqueous solution of KCNS (1.8g.) to yield 1.1 g. of the crystalline product, m.p. 221° (decomp.). (Found: C, 53.51; H, 6.07; N, 12.39; S, 14.6. $C_{10}H_{14}O_2N_2S$ requires C, 53.9; H, 6.19; N, 12.02; S, 14.16%).

dl-6-Ethylpilosinine.—The preceding compound (0.46g.) was oxidised by an aqueous solution of $FeCl_3$ (3 g.) and from the oxidised solution *dl-6-ethylpilosinidine nitrate*, m.p. 146° (with slight decomposition), was obtained; yield 0.36g. (Found: C, 46.51; H, 6.81; N, 16.12. $C_{10}H_{15}O_3N_3$ requires C, 46.51; H, 6.2; N, 16.26%). This nitrate (0.3g.) was made alkaline with 50% K_2CO_3 and extracted with $CHCl_3$ (15c.c. $\times$ 3). The organic layer was dried and the solvent removed. The residue was methylated with methanol (2 c.c.) and CH_3I (0.5 c.c.) in a sealed tube at 50-60°. From this 0.28 g. of white crystalline *dl-6-ethylpilosinine nitrate*, m.p. 141-43°, was obtained. (Found: C, 48.25; H, 6.1; N, 15.70. $C_{11}H_{16}O_3N_3$ requires C, 48.53; H, 6.61; N, 15.44%).